

Tracing the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) Results of San Isidro College Takers from 2016-2022: Strategies for Interventions

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How to cite this paper:

Simbulan, S. (2022). Tracing the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) Results of San Isidro College Takers from 2016-2022: Strategies for Interventions. *School of Education Research Journal*, 3: 1-12.

Received: November 4, 2022

Accepted: December 16, 2022

Published: February 10, 2023

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this study is on tracing the results of the LET of the San Isidro College takers from March 2016 to January 2022, highlighting on the comparison of the school's percentage of passing with that of the National passing rate, as well as the comparison of the rate of passing for the first-time takers with those of the repeaters. The study used the descriptive method of research, data mining the results in the data-base of the Philippine Regulations Commission (PRC). Findings revealed that the teacher education LET takers of San Isidro College showed a comparatively high percentage of passing for both secondary and elementary levels with that of the National Passing rate from 2016 to 2022, however, there are relatively few schedules where the percentage of passing fall short from the national passing rate, hence some intervention strategies are suggested to really strengthen the graduates' readiness for the LET.

Subject Areas

Teaching; Evaluation

Keywords: *Licensure Examination for Teachers, Interventions*

INTRODUCTION

The teacher professionalization Act of 1994 promotes the professional up-scaling of teachers, as well as supervising and regulating the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) administered by the Philippine Regulations Commission (PRC). The LET is an assessment required for teacher education graduate applicants to qualify them to teach in the elementary or secondary. Passing the LET is assumed to measure the competencies as reflected in the National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS) that are needed for effective teaching. The LET passers differentiate

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those who have the skills and are capable in teaching. Passing the LET is one quality assurance indicator for the school's accreditation.

The LET has currently the greatest number of examinees, hence PRC administer the exams twice a year in places and dates determined by the Board of Professional Teachers. The examination has these components: the General Education courses, the Professional Education courses, and the different specialization courses. The secondary education takers have all the 3 components, while the elementary education takers have only the general education and the professional education courses. The examinees for both should obtain an average rating of 75% with no rating of 50% or below in the component subjects. In the elementary level 40% for the general rating comes from the General Education courses and 60% from the professional education. Whereas, in the Secondary level, 20% of the average rating comes from the General Education courses, 40% from the professional education courses, and 40% from the field of specialization (PRC website).

One non-governmental organization, the Philippine Business for Education (PBEd) usually spearheaded research on the LET performance of TEIs across the country since 2009. The organization revealed that the mean passing rate of teacher education graduates since 2009 is only 31%. PBEd also observed that at least half of TEIs perform below the mean national passing rate. TEIs which consistently registered poor performance for five years were even recommended to close their teacher education programs. Similarly, Baylan (2018) studied the trend of LET performance from 2008 to 2017 of leading TEIs across different regions in the Philippines and revealed that a considerable number of TEIs were struggling to attain a 60% national passing standard. Nool and Ladia (2017) also disclosed poor LET performance of 110 TEIs in Central Luzon from 2009 to 2016. With the noticeable gap in the quality of education among TEIs, many researchers looked into the determinants affecting graduates' LET performance to be able to pinpoint which components the TEIs would have to strengthen their teacher education students.

One of the primordial concerns of the School of Education at San Isidro College is to have its graduates pass the LET, since this is one indicator that the school is performing well. With the school's subjecting itself for PAASCU accreditation in 2022, the School of Education (SED) has to retrieve the data of the LET passers for the past 5 years starting in 2016. The CHED as well as the PAASCU accreditors require these data because they wanted to be assured on the effectiveness of the teacher education program that the school is offering. This study therefore traced the performance of the SIC graduates in the LET starting 2016 to 2022. The data mined from the PRC served as the basis for the documentary analysis in tracing the LET performance of the SIC graduates.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The study anchors on the premise that quality is assured when performance is assessed on the learning competencies. Teacher education institutions demonstrate their trademark of quality through the performance of their graduates in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (Amanonce and Maramag, 2020). RA 7836 also known as the "*Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994*", highlights the standards for teacher graduates to qualify for professional teachers by passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET).

Teacher Education graduates who finished Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) are tested along three components in the LET, namely General Education, Professional Education, and Field of Specialization with corresponding weights of 20%, 40%, and 40%, respectively. On the other hand, graduates of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) are assessed along two components which are General Education and Professional Education with corresponding weights of 40% and 60%, respectively. The passing rate for the LET is 75%. Passing this standardized test is not only a requirement to practice the teaching profession but also a guarantee that teachers in the basic education sector possess the necessary competence and professional accountability (Amanonce, et al, 2020). The studies of Antiojo (2017) in Cavite State University and of Guazon and Marpa (2013) in Philippine Normal University concluded that the Major and Professional Education subjects were the areas in the Licensure Examination for Teachers where graduates find difficulty.

Since the government put much premium on teachers passing the LET, most if not all TEIs have to make good in implementing strict admission and retention policies, hiring qualified and competent faculty, conducting curricular reviews, updating of course syllabi, and making suggestions as to how they could improve the students' scores in the LET. Some TEIs conduct audit courses, review classes and mock exams to help prepare their students to pass the LET.

The interplay of LET performance and profile of the school, teachers, and students; teachers' competence; school facilities; curriculum and instruction; and admission and retention policies were significant predictors of passing the licensure examination by teacher education graduates. Also, the demographic profile of the graduates such as gender, age, high school average, and intelligence quotient was also established as determinants of LET performance. Among such researches, the studies of Pachejo and Allaga (2013) disclosed a weak relationship between academic grades and LET performance of teacher education graduates of Rizal Technological University in Mandaluyong, Philippines. Moreover, Apare, Arcilla, and Vasquez (2018) revealed that the GPA of BSEd graduates of Mountain View College in Bukidnon, Philippines is not significantly related to their LET performance along Field of Specialization. Similarly, Visco's (2015) study on determining predictors of LET performance among graduates of TEIs in Abra, Philippines was not able to establish the academic achievement of graduates as a significant predictor of LET performance. The current study traced the performance of the SIC LET results for the past six years highlighting on its comparison vis-à-vis the national passing rate to establish the effectiveness of the teacher education program of the school.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study traced and assessed the LET results of the San Isidro College SED takers for the past six years, starting March 2016 to January 2022. Specifically, it answered the following:

1. What are the LET results of the SIC teacher education graduates for the secondary and elementary level from 2016 to 2022?
2. How do the results of the LET of the SIC graduates compare with the National Passing rate from 2016-2022?
3. How do the first-time takers compare with the repeaters in the LET performance?
4. What strategies for interventions are suggested by the SED faculty for the Teacher Education Program of San Isidro College?

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study served as a documentary analysis of the result of the LET takers of San Isidro College from March 2016 to January 2022. It used the descriptive method of research, employing the data mined from the PRC data base on the takers of the LET examination. From the SIC takers, the total number for the secondary level from 2016 to 2022 was 402 while for the elementary level was 140, giving an overall sum of 542 as reflected in Table 1.

The study was conducted at San Isidro College, School of Education. The school offers the degrees for elementary and secondary education. The secondary education has for 4 major fields of specialization, namely: English, Filipino, Mathematics, and Values Education, while the elementary has the General Education program. Since the teacher education program is a board course, the School of Education (SED) follows the curriculum prescribed by CHED with its prescribed policies, standards and guidelines as reflected in the CMOs 174 and 175. SED also has its policies and guidelines especially on admission and retention to assure quality and be able to pass the LET.

Table 1

San Isidro College Teacher Education Graduates who took the LET in the Secondary Level

SECONDARY	2016		2017		2018		2019		2021	2022	TOTAL
	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Sept	Jan	
1 st Timer	16	24	19	18	19	20	30	14	18	3	181
Repeater	20	35	33	21	23	23	26	24	0	16	221
Total	36	59	52	39	42	43	56	38	18	19	402
ELEMENTARY	2016		2017		2018		2019		2021	2022	TOTAL
	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Sept	Jan	
1 st Timer	0	7	3	8	2	7	6	4	3	5	45
Repeater	20	18	13	11	9	7	10	7	0	0	95
Total	20	25	16	19	11	14	16	11	3	5	140
OVERALL	56	84	68	58	53	57	72	49	21	24	542

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

LET results of the SIC teacher education graduates for the secondary and elementary level from 2016 to 2022

Table 2 reflects the results of San Isidro College LET takers in the secondary level from March 2016 to January 2022. On the one hand, it is noted that the first-time takers achieved a higher percentage of passing compared to the National passing rate. It is only in September 2019 where the passing rate was 35.71% which is 3.98% less than the national passing rate. The rest of the data shows a much higher percentage of passing rate. On the other hand, the repeaters, did not reach the national passing rate except in January 2022 where it obtained a 68.75 % which is 14.46% higher than the national passing rate.

Table 2*LET results of the SIC teacher education graduates for the Secondary level from 2016 to 2022*

Secondary	2016		2017		2018		2019		2021	2022
	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Sept	Jan
First Timers										
Passed	10	9	9	9	13	11	19	5	14	2
Failed	6	15	10	9	6	9	11	9	4	1
Total	16	24	19	18	19	20	30	14	18	3
Passing %	62.50	37.50	47.37	50.00	68.42	55.00	63.33	35.71	77.78	66.67
National Passing	35.43	33.78	25.92	46.37	29.91	48.03	25.95	39.69	57.77	54.29
Repeaters										
Passed	1	5	5	8	3	4	6	7	None	11
Failed	19	30	28	13	20	19	20	17		5
Total	20	35	33	21	23	23	26	24		16
Passing %	5.00	14.29	15.15	38.10	13.04	17.39	23.08	29.17		68.75
National Passing	35.43	33.78	25.92	46.37	29.91	48.03	25.95	39.69		54.29

Table 3 shows the results of San Isidro College LET takers in the elementary level from March 2016 to January 2022. As shown in the table, except for the data in March 2016 where there are no first-time takers, this group achieved a higher percentage of passing compared to the National passing rate in all the LET given from 2016-2022. The repeaters however showed a very poor performance in Sept. 2016, Sept 2017, and Sept 2018 where all the retakers failed the LET. In September 2021 and January 2022, there were no repeaters; hence the overall result for the elementary was very high. In fact, in January 2022, the elementary takers got a 100% passing rate.

Table 3*LET results of the SIC teacher education graduates for the Elementary level from 2016 to 2022*

Secondary	2016		2017		2018		2019		2021	2022
	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Sept	Jan
First Timers										
Passed	0	4	1	3	1	2	5	4	2	5
Failed	0	3	2	5	1	5	1	0	1	0
Total	0	7	3	8	2	7	6	4	3	5
Passing %	0.00	57.14	33.33	37.50	50.00	28.57	83.33	100	66.67	100
National Passing	28.39	30.18	10.39	26.33	23.62	20.29	27.29	31.34	55.96	56.90
Repeaters										
Passed	8	0	2	0	5	0	4	1	None	None
Failed	12	18	11	11	4	7	6	6		
Total	20	18	13	11	9	7	10	7		
Passing %	40.00	0.00	15.38	0.00	55.56	0.00	40.00	14.29		
National Passing	28.39	30.18	10.39	26.33	23.62	20.29	27.29	31.34		

Comparative analysis on the Percentage of passing of the SIC LET takers with the National Passing rate from 2016-2022

Table 4 illustrates the results of the LET for the SIC takers both in the secondary and elementary level vis-à-vis the national passing rate percentage. It is noted that in the secondary level the overall SIC LET takers for both first timers and repeaters have a higher percentage of passing from the National passing rate in March 2017 with a difference of 1%; March 2018 with

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a difference of 8.19%; March 2019 with a difference of 18.68%; Sept 2021 with a difference of 20.02%; January 2022 with a difference of 14.13%, all in favor of the SIC takers. This indicates that the SIC takers had surpassed the national passing rate during these schedules of the LET. The highest difference of percentage happened on September 2021, closely followed in March 2019 and January 2021. If one will revisit the results of the first timers in Table 2, it is only in September 2019 where the first takers did not reach the National Passing rate. However, when the overall result for the first timers and repeaters were combined, the final results showed that the SIC takers passed in March 2017, March 2018, March 2019, September 2021 and January 2022. In Septembers 2016, 2017, and 2018, all the repeaters did not pass the LET. In the other schedules, it is observed that the repeaters who failed were more than the repeaters who passed. This result indicated that the repeaters pulled down the results of the LET for SIC takers.

Table 4
Results of the LET of SIC compared with the National Passing rate

Secondary	2016		2017		2018		2019		2021	2022
	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Sept	Jan
Overall										
Passed	11	14	14	17	16	15	25	12	14	13
Failed	25	45	38	22	26	28	31	26	4	6
Total	36	59	52	39	42	43	56	38	18	19
Passing %	30.56	23.73	26.92	43.59	38.10	34.88	44.64	31.58	77.78	68.42
National Passing	35.43	33.78	25.92	46.37	29.91	48.03	25.95	39.69	57.77	54.29
Elementary	2016		2017		2018		2019		2021	2022
	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Sept	Jan
Overall										
Passed	8	4	3	3	6	2	9	5	2	5
Failed	12	21	13	16	5	12	7	6	1	0
Total	20	25	16	19	11	14	16	11	3	5
Passing %	40.00	16.00	18.75	15.79	54.55	14.29	56.25	45.45	66.67	100
National Passing	28.39	30.18	10.39	26.33	23.62	20.29	27.29	31.34	55.96	56.90

For the elementary level the overall SIC LET takers for both first timers and repeaters have a higher percentage of passing from the National passing rate in March 2016 with a difference of 11.61%; March 2017 with a difference of 8.36%; March 2018 with a difference of 30.93%; March 2019 with a difference of 28.96%; September 2019 with a difference of 14.11; September 2021 with a difference of 10.71%; January 2022 with a difference of 43.1%, all in favor of the SIC takers. It is also noted that in January 2022, the elementary SIC takers got a 100% passing rate. As observed earlier in Table 3 the elementary first timer takers surpassed the National passing rates in all the schedules. However, in September 2016, September 2017, and September 2018 the SIC repeaters all failed in this examination hence pulling down the overall result of the LET for SIC. Without the repeaters in Sept 2021 and January 2022, the results were very high compared to the National Passing rate.

Overall, the Secondary LET takers of SIC passed the LET in March 2017, March 2018, March 2019, Sept. 2021 and January 2022; while the elementary takers passed in March 2016, March 2017, March 2018, March 2019, September 2019, September 2021 and January 2022;

Comparative Analysis of the results of SIC LET takers between the first-time takers and the repeaters

Comparing the results of the SIC LET takers who are first timers with the repeaters, Table 5 shows that the first timers in the secondary level have percentages higher than the national passing scores in most schedules of the LET. It is only in Sept 2019 where the percentage is lower than the national passing rate. Likewise, for the elementary level all the first timers in the different schedules got percentages above the National percentage in all the LET schedules. Whereas, the repeaters got a zero percentage of passing in Septembers 2016, 2017, and 2018

Table 5

SIC LET first-time takers compared with the repeaters in the LET

Secondary	2016		2017		2018		2019		2021	2022
	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Sept	Jan
First Timers	62.50	37.50	47.37	50	68.42	55	63.33	35.71	77.78	66.67
Repeaters	5.00	14.29	15.15	38.10	13.04	17.39	23.08	29.17	None	68.75
National Passing	35.43	33.78	25.92	46.37	29.91	48.03	25.95	39.69	57.77	54.29

Elementary	2016		2017		2018		2019		2021	2022
	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Mar	Sept	Sept	Jan
First Timers	0	57.14	33.33	37.50	50	28.57	83.33	100	66.67	100
Repeaters	40.00	0.00	15.38	0.00	55.56	0.00	40.00	14.29	None	None
National Passing	28.39	30.18	10.39	26.33	23.62	20.29	27.29	31.34	55.96	56.90

Based from the data provided by the PRC, there are education graduate takers who failed to achieve the cut-off score of 75%. The first-time takers often experience failures. However, there were several instances where re-takers caused the failure of the group to reach the national passing rate because their scores pull down the result of the whole group.

Secondary graduates generally have 3 subjects to take: the Professional subject, the General Education subject, and the major subject and they spend the whole day to take the exam. Often, they are bogged down in their major subject. In the January 2022 LET Exam, the school was able to produce a 4th placer in the LET for the secondary level in Values Education. This first-time achievement marked a memorable milestone for San Isidro College inspiring the students to perform well in the future licensure examination for teachers,

From the list of names listed as takers by PRC, there were re-takers who have taken the LET a number of times and still failed. Table 6 shows the number of times some secondary level LET takers failed and retake the exam. There were examinees that took the exam every year and failed. Some have taken the exam 8 times before they pass the LET. It is observed that the column on “*first take and failed*” had the most number. This means that they did not pass the first take. Some still failed the second take, or the third take, and so on.

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Table 6

Number of Secondary level SIC LET takers who failed /re-take the LET

Month/Year	1 st take	2 nd take	3 rd take	4 th take	5 th take	6 th take	7 th take	8 th take	TOTAL
March 2016	5	10	4	3		1	1	1	25
September 2016	10	13	3	2					28
March 2017	12	3	1		1				17
September 2017	4		4	2					10
March 2018	5	2	3	1					11
September 2018	10	3	1						14
March 2019	10	4							14
September 2019	11								11
TOTAL	67	35	16	8	1	1	1	1	131

It is noted that in March 2016, of the 25 takers who failed, five of these take it for the first time and failed, 10 have taken it twice and failed, 4 have taken it 3 times and still failed, 3 have taken it 4 times, one had taken it 6 times, one had it 7 times, and 1 had taken it 8 times and failed. In September 2016, 10 students took it for the first time and failed, 13 took it for the 2nd time and still failed, 4 took it for the 3rd time and 2 took it for the 4th time, yet they still failed. Usually, it is in the first take where students have much failure. Still, there are those who have taken for the 2nd or 3rd time and still they failed. Scrutinizing the list of those who failed, there were names of the same student who did the retaking every exam period and still failed. It could be deduced that the student who kept on failing just took the exam without adequate review and preparation. They just took the exam with the thinking that they might pass this time. Taking the exam by chance is not a guarantee that they will pass the exam this time because they have taken this several times. SIC has no control on LET re-takers and it just hope that those retaking the exam will pass.

Table 7

Number of Elementary levels SIC LET takers who failed or re-take the LET

Month/Year	1 st take	2 nd take	3 rd take	4 th take	5 th take	6 th take	TOTAL
March 2016	4	3	2	2			11
September 2016	6	4	2		1	1	14
March 2017	3	1					4
September 2017	7			2			9
March 2018	1						1
September 2018	6	1					7
March 2019	4						4
September 2019	3						3
TOTAL	34	9	4	4	1	1	54

In the elementary level, the students have only 2 subjects to take; The General Education courses and the Professional Education courses. It is often in the first take where students have failures, yet still there are those who have done two takes or 3 and 4 takes, yet they still failed. There are daring takers who have done 5 and 6 retakes. This phenomenon seems to indicate that there are LET takers who dare to retake the exam even if they are not well-prepared to take this. The effect of this phenomenon is disadvantageous for the school because it could pull down the general score, giving a detrimental effect of not reaching the national passing rate. Not reaching the national passing rate would indicate failure for the school which is not a good picture for marketing the school to the general public. At the same time, quality assurance is jeopardized,

disqualifying the school to be numbered among the regular passers. And, if the school does not pass the exam for three consecutive years it could be advised to stop its operation.

Strategies for interventions suggested by the SED faculty for the Teacher Education Program of San Isidro College

The SED faculty in one of the meetings suggested intervention strategies for the Teacher Education Program to strengthen the performance of the SED takers for the LET. Matrix 1 shows some of these suggested intervention strategies:

Matrix 1

Intervention strategies to prepare SED LET takers for the LET

Suggested Strategies	Activities
1. Yearly assessment of the students/ End-of-the year assessment of the students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There will be a MOCK Licensure examination from first up to 4th year conducted preferably right after the 2nd semester ends or summer time • Teachers will prepare the assessment examinations based from the content in the syllabi following the format of the Licensure examination • From 1st to 3rd year, there could only be 25-30 item multiple-choice exam each for the Prof Ed, Gen Ed and major subjects prepared from the contribution of teachers. A Committee could prepare the TOS and consolidate the items contributed by the teachers. • Teachers handling the Gen. Ed, Prof Ed. and Majors will have to contribute the multiple-choice items based from the content of the course. There should be a TOS for the examinations given • The final draft of the exam will be validated by the committee and the reliability test will be conducted prior to the finalization of the items. • Similar answer sheet provided by the PRC LET will be used by the students to answer their yearly evaluation exam. This will familiarize them with the actual conduct of the exam. • The cut-off score will serve as the basis to decide if the student passed or failed the exam. • If the student will not pass the MOCK exam, he/she is advised to study/review to retake this. If after two takes he/she still fails the exam, he/she will be put on probationary status. • The results will be posted in the SED Bulletin Board after one week's time. • For the Secondary Education, the exam will have the format of the LET: Subject 1- Gen Ed, Subject 2- Prof Ed, Subject 3- major courses • For the Elementary Education, the exam will have the format of the LET: Subject 1- Gen Ed, Subject 2- Prof Ed

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- | | |
|---|---|
| 2. MOCK- LET Exam for graduating students | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Fourth year/graduating students will have to take the final MOCK LET Examination to check if they are ready/prepare for the Real LET exam• The same number of days and time allotment will be simulated for the MOCK LET Exam• The same procedure for the preparation of the exams and the process for content validity and reliability will be taken prior to the finalization of the items.• To pass the exam, an examinee must obtain an average rating of not less than 75% and must have no rating of lower than 50% in any of the test• Teachers/Proctors will be assigned to conduct the MOCK Exam preferably after the finals/summer time• Room assignment will be made together with the list of takers in the particular room.• If a student fails the exam, he/she will be advised that his/her TOR will only bear FOR REFERENCE/FOR WORK ONLY. It will NOT bear FOR LET/PRC EXAM. This will be coordinated with the registrar. The list of passers and non-passers will be given to the Registrar so that they could put the appropriate Remarks in the TOR.• A student who failed the MOCK exam should not take the LET if he/she is not ready and has not done a very good review. Once the student is ready, he/she has to present a proof to the registrar that he/she is undertaking a review and his/her performance shows that he/she is ready to take the LET. |
| 3. External Review by the student | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Even if the student passed the SIC MOCK LET Exam, he/she is still advised to have his/her Review in the Review Center of his/her choice• The students should really prepare for the LET exam and must aim to pass this or even be on the top list as passers• The student should update SIC–SED on his status as to when (date/year) he/she is going to take the LET so that he/she will be included in the prayer petitions to pass the Board Exam |
| 4. Incentives | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The school could request the administration for monetary incentives to topnotch (top 10) passers of the LET Exam. An Awarding Program will also be given.• Topnotch students will be posted in the social media as example of academic excellence students worthy of emulation from other students in the lower years; their achievement will also be posted in the SIC and SED advertisement bulletin board |

- Three consecutive Consistent 100% passing rate for the program will get CHED's recognition/award.
- For the committee/teachers who will prepare the exam with TOS; reliability result; item analysis result; and the answer sheets, the school administration will be requested to provide an incentive honorarium for their outputs. The output will be properly kept for confidentiality of items for the exam
- The MOCK LET will be properly scheduled ahead of time with the list of takers posted in the rooms assigned for this, similarly as in the real LET exam. The schedule will be posted in the SED Bulletin Board. Focal person/faculty will be assigned to do the updates.
- For the teachers assigned as proctors during the Mock LET exam, the school administration will be requested to provide snacks, lunch, and honorarium corresponding to the number of hours they have rendered

CONCLUSION

Of the 542 BSEd and BEEd LET-takers of San Isidro College from March 2016-January 2022, one hundred fifty-one (28%) from the secondary and forty-seven (9%) from the elementary, totaling to 198 (37%) takers passed the LET, with the National passing rate as the gauge of the cut-off score. This result may not be ideal to assure that the graduates at San Isidro College are performing adequately in the LET. While the LET results for both the secondary and elementary levels revealed that the first-time takers have a higher rate of percentage passing when compared to the national passing rate, still there are those who failed the test. The first-time takers comparatively showed a higher percentage of passing rate when compared with the repeaters. The overall result however is pulled down by the performance of the repeaters who despite several retakes still were not able to make it. The school has no more hold of the repeaters but it can strengthen the number of passers from the first-time takers by providing some intervention strategies to achieve a 100% passing rate from them.

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